

Appendix A: Prompts for ChatGPT Content Coding on Insider Threat Text

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This appendix contains the ChatGPT prompts used in *Integrating Computational Text Analysis into Risk and Crisis Communication Development* (to be submitted to the 26th Annual IEEE Conference on Information Reuse & Integration (IRI)). The first prompt identifies insider threat characters that fit as one of three character types: Hero, Victim, and Villain. All character type definitions come from the Narrative Policy Framework (NPF) [1]. The next three prompts are variations of the same task: classify insider threat source text as one or more NPF character types based on the characters identified in the previous step. We investigate three versions of the same prompt to assess performance compared to human coders performing the same task.

We present the prompts below:

Algorithm 1 PROMPT FOR IDENTIFYING CHARACTERS(*idx*, *message*, *charType*, *section*)

Require: *idx*, index of the insider threat text (section level)

message, the insider threat text (section level)

charType, Hero, Victim, or Villain label

section, hazard information section

Ensure: Prompt to identify characters within insider threat text

return f“““ msgID: ‘{*idx*}’

memMessage: ‘{*message*}’

Researchers asked people to personally define insider threats, describe their own risk perceptions and impacts of insider threats, and provide solutions to counter insider threats within their organization.

Researchers also gathered authoritative text on insider threats and grouped text into one of three sections: Problem Definition, Risk Perception, and Solutions.

Problem Definition refers to how entities define a given hazard including what it is, what risk factors are associated with a hazard, and how entities are impacted by the hazard.

Risk Perception refers to how entities perceive the risk of a hazard on an individual and community level.

Solutions refer to intended and actual behavior exhibited by entities to protect themselves and their community from a hazard. It also refers to entities’ self-efficacy when faced with a hazard.

The messages presented fall under the content group {*section*}.

Identify entities in the message that play role of ‘{*charType*}’. Do not provide explanations for the entity identified.

Heroes are entities, individuals, or groups that provide support, correct information, or positive actions to mitigate suffering or negative impacts of insider threats.

Villains are entities, individuals, or groups that cause harm, spread misinformation, or hinder positive efforts.

Victims are entities, individuals, or groups that have suffered harm or loss due to insider threats.

Non-specific pronouns such as “you” or “our” or “one” in the text may refer to the author or general public if the pronoun meets roles of ‘{*charType*}’ For example, statements such as “monitor data” or “create a secure password” have an implied “you” that refers to the individual citizen or public which can play roles of hero.

Importantly, list only the entity’s name without additional descriptions.

Lastly, please only list entities that align with ‘{*charType*}’. Do not add additional character types.”””

Algorithm 2 PROMPT FOR CLASSIFYING SENTENCES v1(*idx, hero, victim, villain*)

Require: *text*, the insider threat text (sentence level)

hero, list of insider threat hero characters

victim, list of insider threat victim characters

villain, list of insider threat villain characters

Ensure: Prompt to classify sentences as one or more character types

return f“““ Researchers asked people to personally define insider threats, describe their own risk perceptions and impacts of insider threats, and provide solutions to counter insider threats within their organization.

Researchers also gathered authoritative text on insider threats.

Determine if the text ‘*{text}*’ best fits one or more of the following NPF-defined character types: Hero, Victim, or Villain.

Heroes are entities, individuals, or groups that provide support, correct information, or positive actions to mitigate suffering or negative impacts of insider threats.

Some hero characters that can be present in the context of insider threats include: ‘*{hero}*’

Villains are entities, individuals, or groups that cause harm, spread misinformation, or hinder positive efforts.

Some victim characters that can be present in the context of insider threats include: ‘*{victim}*’

Victims are entities, individuals, or groups that have suffered harm or loss due to insider threats.

Some villain characters that can be present in the context of insider threats include: ‘*{villain}*’

Non-specific pronouns such as “you” or “our” or “one” in the text may refer to the author or general public if the pronoun meets roles of Hero, Victim, or Villain.

For example, statements such as “monitor data” or ”create a secure password” have an implied “you” that refers to the individual citizen or public which can play roles of hero.

If the text doesn’t fit least one NPF character type, return the character type as ‘NO TYPE’

If the text doesn’t have any clear NPF character types, return the character type as ‘UNCLEAR’.

If the text fits more than one NPF character type, return the character types in the following format: ‘characterType1 & characterType2’ for two or ‘characterType1 & characterType2 & characterType3’ for three.

Lastly, just return the character type or types and only the character type(s) as your response (for example, if the character type is ‘Hero’, just return Hero; or if the character type is ‘Hero’ and ‘Victim’, just return ‘Hero & Victim’).”””

Algorithm 3 PROMPT FOR CLASSIFYING SENTENCES v2(*idx, hero, victim, villain*)

Require: *text*, the insider threat text (sentence level)

hero, list of insider threat hero characters

victim, list of insider threat victim characters

villain, list of insider threat villain characters

Ensure: Prompt to classify sentences as one or more character types

return f“““ Researchers asked people to personally define insider threats, describe their own risk perceptions and impacts of insider threats, and provide solutions to counter insider threats within their organization.

Researchers also gathered authoritative text on insider threats.

Determine if the text ‘*{text}*’ best fits one or more of the following NPF-defined character types: Hero, Victim, or Villain.

Heroes are entities, individuals, or groups that provide support, correct information, or positive actions to mitigate suffering or negative impacts of insider threats.

Some hero characters that can be present in the context of insider threats include: ‘*{hero}*’

Villains are entities, individuals, or groups that cause harm, spread misinformation, or hinder positive efforts.

Some victim characters that can be present in the context of insider threats include: ‘*{victim}*’

Victims are entities, individuals, or groups that have suffered harm or loss due to insider threats.

Some villain characters that can be present in the context of insider threats include: ‘*{villain}*’

Non-specific pronouns such as “you” or “our” or “one” in the text may refer to the author or general public if the pronoun meets roles of Hero, Victim, or Villain.

For example, statements such as “monitor data” or ”create a secure password” have an implied “you” that refers to the individual citizen or public which can play roles of hero.

If the text doesn’t have any clear NPF character types, return the character type as ‘UNCLEAR’.

If the text fits more than one NPF character type, return the character types in the following format: ‘characterType1 & characterType2’ for two or ‘characterType1 & characterType2 & characterType3’ for three.

Lastly, just return the character type or types and only the character type(s) as your response (for example, if the character type is ‘Hero’, just return Hero; or if the character type is ‘Hero’ and ‘Victim’, just return ‘Hero & Victim’).”””

Algorithm 4 PROMPT FOR CLASSIFYING SENTENCES v3(*idx, hero, victim, villain*)

Require: *text*, the insider threat text (sentence level)

hero, list of insider threat hero characters

victim, list of insider threat victim characters

villain, list of insider threat villain characters

Ensure: Prompt to classify sentences as one or more character types

return f“““ Researchers asked people to personally define insider threats, describe their own risk perceptions and impacts of insider threats, and provide solutions to counter insider threats within their organization.

Researchers also gathered authoritative text on insider threats.

Determine if the text ‘*text*’ best fits one or more of the following NPF-defined character types: Hero, Victim, or Villain.

Heroes are entities, individuals, or groups that provide support, correct information, or positive actions to mitigate suffering or negative impacts of insider threats.

Some hero characters that can be present in the context of insider threats include: ‘*hero*’

Villains are entities, individuals, or groups that cause harm, spread misinformation, or hinder positive efforts.

Some victim characters that can be present in the context of insider threats include: ‘*victim*’

Victims are entities, individuals, or groups that have suffered harm or loss due to insider threats.

Some villain characters that can be present in the context of insider threats include: ‘*villain*’

Non-specific pronouns such as “you” or “our” or “one” in the text may refer to the author or general public if the pronoun meets roles of Hero, Victim, or Villain.

For example, statements such as “monitor data” or ”create a secure password” have an implied “you” that refers to the individual citizen or public which can play roles of hero.

If the text fits more than one NPF character type, return the character types in the following format: ‘characterType1 & characterType2’ for two or ‘characterType1 & characterType2 & characterType3’ for three.

Lastly, just return the character type or types and only the character type(s) as your response (for example, if the character type is ‘Hero’, just return Hero; or if the character type is ‘Hero’ and ‘Victim’, just return ‘Hero & Victim’).”””

References

- [1] Elizabeth A. Shanahan, Michael D. Jones, Mark K. McBeth, and Claudio M. Radaelli. The narrative policy framework. In Christopher M. Weible and Paul A. Sabatier, editors, *Theories of the Policy Process*, chapter 5. Routledge, New York, 2018.

Appendix B: Human Coding Process for Insider Threat Text

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This appendix details the coding process the human coders performed in *Integrating Computational Text Analysis into Risk and Crisis Communication Development* (to be submitted to the 26th Annual IEEE Conference on Information Reuse & Integration (IRI)). The instructions provided below were followed to code insider threat-related text according to the Narrative Policy Framework (NPF) [1]. This process involved three main tasks:

1 Identifying NPF Characters in Stratified 20% Section-Level Text

The section-level text provided by the lead author as a spreadsheet was analyzed to categorize entities into one of three NPF character types:

- Hero – Entities that take positive actions to mitigate insider threats.
- Victim – Entities that have suffered harm due to insider threats.
- Villain – Entities that cause harm, spread misinformation, or hinder positive efforts.

For each section (Problem Definition, Risk Perception, and Solutions), coders:

- Identified entities playing a specific character role.
- Recorded these entities under their respective columns in the spreadsheet.

2 Classifying Character Phrases in Stratified 10% Sentence-Level Text

Using the sentence-level text spreadsheet provided by the lead author, each phrase was classified as one of the three character types based on:

- The presence of identified Hero, Victim, or Villain characters.
- The phrasing of the sentence to determine the most fitting character classification.
- Sentences with no apparent character were coded as ‘None’.
- Sentences with a character but its designation was not clear were coded as ‘Unclear’.
- The assigned character type was recorded under the column “npf_char_type” in the spreadsheet.

3 Inter-Coder Reliability Assessment

- The coded data was compared with another trained coder’s work to assess agreement.
- Coders talked through disagreement to meet a consensus.
- Sentences where both coders agreed were finalized in an aggregated spreadsheet.

References

- [1] Elizabeth A. Shanahan, Michael D. Jones, Mark K. McBeth, and Claudio M. Radaelli. The narrative policy framework. In Christopher M. Weible and Paul A. Sabatier, editors, *Theories of the Policy Process*, chapter 5. Routledge, New York, 2018.

Appendix C: TF-IDF Results for Stemmed and Nonstemmed ngrams

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This Appendix contains extra tables displaying the TF-IDF for the top three stemmed and nonstemmed ngrams investigated in *Integrating Computational Text Analysis into Risk and Crisis Communication Development* (to be submitted to the 26th Annual IEEE Conference on Information Reuse & Integration (IRI)). The ngrams investigated are potential characters defined by the Narrative Policy Framework (NPF) [3] and found within insider threat hazard information sections. These characters can take the role of Hero, Victim, Villain, or any combination of the three; hazard sections are Problem Definitions, Risk Perceptions, and Solutions. Identifying key characters within insider threat text helps with future risk and crisis communication (RCC) message development [2].

In *Integrating computational text analysis into risk and crisis communication*, we report the top three nonstemmed character bigrams across sections. Our reasoning for its inclusion is that (1) stemming ngrams can lose important contextual information [5], which is key for determining how characters and character language frame future risk messaging [4], and (2) we find that unigrams and trigrams can reveal too little information on characters and character language. For unigrams, while one word can be associated with a character (e.g., “IT”, “hacker”, “laboratory”) or character language (e.g., “feel”, “attack”, “help”), the context that a single word is used in can be lost. For trigrams, while more context can be present for characters (e.g., “compromised organization employees”, “social engineering attack”) and character language (e.g., “I feel educated”, “They cause harm”), we find trigrams to be useful for uncovering character language, not characters themselves (Table 3). We also find that some unigrams are also not meaningful in identifying

characters or language (Table 1).

Regarding ngram relevance, the frequency of their appearance does not always correlate to the importance of their inclusion in future risk messages. Term frequency scores given by TF-IDF analysis correspond to that term’s frequency with respect to the document(s) it appears in [1]. That is, the most effective characters and character language to include in RCC messaging could be ranked mathematically lower than expected.

We present tables for the top three stemmed uni-, bi, and trigrams and top three nonstemmed uni- and trigrams below:

Table 1: Top Three Character Type Unigrams across the Section Corpora based on TF-IDF (Nonstemmed)

Character Type	Problem Definition		Risk Perception		Solutions	
	<i>Unigram</i>	<i>TF-IDF</i>	<i>Unigram</i>	<i>TF-IDF</i>	<i>Unigram</i>	<i>TF-IDF</i>
Hero	“door”	0.229	“feel”	0.446	“sort”	0.119
	“flagged”	0.211	“compromising”	0.246	“threat”	0.116
	“word”	0.189	“vigilant”	0.215	“things”	0.106
Victim	“found”	0.203	“feel”	0.299	“controls”	0.165
	“mind”	0.189	“things”	0.159	“sort”	0.147
	“insider”	0.163	“cyber”	0.147	“super”	0.144
Villain	“things”	0.187	“compromising”	0.312	“backing”	0.240
	“data”	0.167	“possibly”	0.278	“months”	0.195
	“set”	0.152	“recognize”	0.264	“things”	0.179

Table 2: Top Three Character Type Unigrams across the Section Corpora based on TF-IDF (Stemmed)

Character Type	Problem Definition		Risk Perception		Solutions	
	<i>Unigram</i>	<i>TF-IDF</i>	<i>Unigram</i>	<i>TF-IDF</i>	<i>Unigram</i>	<i>TF-IDF</i>
Hero	“door”	0.229	“feel”	0.354	“thing”	0.139
	“flag”	0.211	“tech”	0.203	“click”	0.134
	“insid”	0.192	“team”	0.189	“sort”	0.119
Victim	“found”	0.203	“feel”	0.309	“train”	0.154
	“insid”	0.190	“cyber”	0.147	“sort”	0.147
	“mind”	0.189	“thing”	0.142	“super”	0.144
Villain	“permiss”	0.214	“send”	0.312	“thing”	0.228
	“manag”	0.195	“possibli”	0.278	“month”	0.195
	“thing”	0.170	“recogn”	0.264	“data”	0.176

Table 3: Top Three Character Type Trigrams across the Section Corpora based on TF-IDF (Nonstemmed)

Character Type	Problem Definition		Risk Perception		Solutions	
	<i>Trigram</i>	<i>TF-IDF</i>	<i>Trigram</i>	<i>TF-IDF</i>	<i>Trigram</i>	<i>TF-IDF</i>
Hero	“emails organization flagged”	0.176	“position vigilant groups”	0.440	“analyze human standpoint”	0.139
	“feel biggest things”	0.155	“feel educated feel”	0.240	“designed cyber secure”	0.139
	“consequences leak proprietary”	0.139	“advantage small team”	0.110	“department evaluate consistently”	0.066
Victim	“experienced consequences firsthand”	0.164	“feel big threat”	0.203	“extra measures research”	0.102
	“firsthand heard consequences”	0.164	“compromising data careful”	0.155	“time talking people”	0.102
	“leak proprietary information”	0.132	“unusual work patterns”	0.110	“change vigilant feel”	0.071
Villain	“indicators compromise feel”	0.165	“delete stuff recognize”	0.660	“dealing sensitive data”	0.147
	“indicators biggest issue”	0.147	“possibly compromising data”	0.203	“administrative headache overhead”	0.139
	“accessing properly protecting”	0.115	“damage pose greater”	0.091	“jump bunch hoops”	0.139

Table 4: Top Three Character Type Trigrams across the Section Corpora based on TF-IDF (Stemmed)

Character Type	Problem Definition		Risk Perception		Solutions	
	<i>Trigram</i>	<i>TF-IDF</i>	<i>Trigram</i>	<i>TF-IDF</i>	<i>Trigram</i>	<i>TF-IDF</i>
Hero	“emails organization flag”	0.176	“position vigilant group”	0.440	“analyze human standpoint”	0.139
	“feel biggest th”	0.155	“feel educated feel”	0.240	“designed cyber secur”	0.139
	“consequences leak proprietary”	0.139	“advantage small team”	0.110	“department evaluate consist”	0.066
Victim	“experienced consequences firsthand”	0.164	“feel big threat”	0.203	“extra measures research”	0.102
	“firsthand heard consequ”	0.164	“compromising data car”	0.155	“time talking peopl”	0.102
	“leak proprietary inform”	0.132	“unusual work pattern”	0.110	“change vigilant feel”	0.071
Villain	“indicators compromise feel”	0.165	“delete stuff recogn”	0.660	“dealing sensitive data”	0.147
	“indicators biggest issu”	0.147	“possibly compromising data”	0.203	“administrative headache overhead”	0.139
	“accessing properly protect”	0.115	“damage pose great”	0.091	“jump bunch hoop”	0.139

Note: Stemming for trigrams performed poorly, hence our decision to forgo reporting on it.

Table 5: Top Three Character Type Bigrams across the Section Corpora based on TF-IDF (Stemmed)

Character Type	Problem Definition		Risk Perception		Solutions	
	<i>Bigram</i>	<i>TF-IDF</i>	<i>Bigram</i>	<i>TF-IDF</i>	<i>Bigram</i>	<i>TF-IDF</i>
Hero	“indicator person”	0.251	“compromising data”	0.365	“send email”	0.112
	“insider threat”	0.144	“vigilant group”	0.293	“quality cod”	0.106
	“shared serv”	0.143	“cyber threat”	0.221	“person concern”	0.075
Victim	“negligent data”	0.120	“compromising data”	0.164	“job posit”	0.180
	“organization log”	0.120	“feel educ”	0.147	“resourcing peopl”	0.115
	“information leav”	0.115	“cyber attack”	0.139	“research lab”	0.091
Villain	“indicator person”	0.139	“compromising data”	0.453	“backing th”	0.264
	“adept technologi”	0.120	“delete stuff”	0.377	“taking extra”	0.133
	“easy click”	0.120	“high risk”	0.165	“external hard”	0.132

References

- [1] Juan Ramos. Using tf-idf to determine word relevance in document queries. In *Proceedings of the first instructional conference on machine learning*, volume 242, pages 29–48. Citeseer, 2003.
- [2] Ann Marie Reinhold, Madison H. Munro, Elizabeth A. Shanahan, Ross J. Gore, Barry C. Ezell, and Clemente I. Izurieta. Embedding software engineering in mixed methods research: Computationally enhanced risk communication. *IJMRA*, 15(2):67–72, 2023.
- [3] Elizabeth A. Shanahan, Michael D. Jones, Mark K. McBeth, and Claudio M. Radaelli. The narrative policy framework. In Christopher M. Weible and Paul A. Sabatier, editors, *Theories of the Policy Process*, chapter 5. Routledge, New York, 2018.
- [4] Elizabeth A. Shanahan, Ann Marie Reinhold, Eric D. Raile, Geoffrey C. Poole, Richard C. Ready, Clemente Izurieta, Jamie McEvoy, Nicolas T. Bergmann, and Henry King. Characters matter: How narratives shape affective responses to risk communication. *PLOS ONE*, 14(12):1–24, 12 2019.
- [5] Jasmeet Singh and Vishal Gupta. Text stemming: Approaches, applications, and challenges. *ACM Comput. Surv.*, 49(3), September 2016.